

TO TEACH ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS TO DRAW PATTERN ELEMENTS STEP BY STEP USING DOTS.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562780>

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Annotation. *This article provides information on ways to simplify the teaching of pattern elements to primary school students in general secondary education.*

Keyword. *Perspective, composition, miniature, architecture.*

It is known that art develops only on the basis of many years of traditions of several generations, the knowledge of the master to the student. This indicates that it has developed in the form of professional art education, although not necessarily in the field of general art education. The reasons for the interruptions in the development of art in Uzbekistan at certain times date back to Alexander the Great, the Mongols, the Arabs and the Russian invaders. This is evidenced by the fact that miniature art flourished during the reign of Amir Temur in the central state. 'rsatdi. As a result, along with Samarkand, Bukhara, Herat miniature schools, Baghdad, Tabriz, Sheroz, Azerbaijan, India, Isfahan, Turkish miniature schools were formed and developed. Although these miniature schools are professionally developed from the arts, they can be easily used in the teaching of fine arts in the general education system. In particular, the curricula developed for general secondary schools include the basics of art, painting and pencil drawing, nature-based imagery, and perceptions of being, and a strong distinction between professional art and general art education systems. the limit cannot be set. Theoretical foundations of fine arts, such as color, size, perspective, and composition, are studied in both the professional and general education systems. Only in the teaching of fine arts should be taken into account the age, cognition, psychological characteristics, visual skills of students and children. The purpose of the subject of fine arts in general secondary schools is to form a harmoniously developed person, his artistic culture. The subject of fine arts provides the knowledge and skills of the elements of artistic culture that everyone needs. Because every student, regardless of the field in which he will work in the future, he will have to rest, relax, and restore the energy expended during work. He achieves this by getting acquainted with, mastering, and enjoying high-quality works of art in museums, exhibitions, and other places. is coming. Drawing is important not only for artists, designers and architects, but also for teachers, engineers, medical workers, builders, agronomists, the military and scientists. In their work, each of them tries to describe their ideas and thoughts, which can not be explained in words, through drawings, diagrams and sketches. However, this does not mean that schools should provide deep and extensive knowledge and skills in the fine, applied and architectural arts. But the fine arts and their forms give a person pleasure. One of them is decorative painting, which has a great opportunity to educate students

artistically. Because in such classes, students learn about the art form, especially its peculiarities. Students will also learn about the means of expression in the arts, such as rhythm, symmetry, asymmetry, and plot. Decorative work plays a key role in developing students' creative abilities.

The visual arts program includes a number of topics, such as drawing a pattern based on the expected shape rework, making a decorative sketch of a box, and making a sketch of a poster or album. For example, in passing on the topic of artistic decoration of a book, the teacher informs that the book is a means of disseminating artistic information, ideas and knowledge, as well as its role in people's lives. The instructive source emphasizes that people are a means of communication. Themes of applied arts have a great opportunity to educate students artistically. Because in such classes, students learn about the art form, especially its peculiarities. At the same time, the students will gain knowledge of the means of expression in the applied arts, such as rhythm, symmetry, asymmetry, plot. Patterns on the theme of applied arts play a key role in developing students' creative abilities.

The visual arts program includes a number of topics, such as drawing a pattern based on the expected shape rework, making a decorative sketch of a box, and making a sketch of a poster or album. For example, in passing on the topic of artistic decoration of a book, the teacher informs that the book is a means of disseminating artistic information, ideas and knowledge, as well as its role in people's lives. The instructive source emphasizes that people are a means of communication. It is not uncommon for a teacher to draw on a compulsory or free subject topic. Students describe their attitudes toward objects with great interest. However, this age group has a negative impact on students' personal development of their fine visual skills. That is why it is important for a fine arts teacher to focus on shaping children to be critical of their fine arts skills.

Fine arts classes help students develop an aesthetic sense of beauty, an interest in art, and an interest in art. The visual arts play a key role in students' social life. Students will be able to use the knowledge and skills they have acquired in class and out of class to develop their passion and ability to create art. Talented children are formed, and then in their free time they have the opportunity to engage in art in clubs, optional classes. The general pedagogical tasks of the subject of fine arts mentioned above include visual memory, observation, figurative thinking, the ability to develop spatial concepts in a systematic and purposeful way, which form the basis for the formation of students' creative abilities.

At present, the issue of interdisciplinary communication is one of the most pressing issues in improving the effectiveness of the course. The rapid development of science and technology culture in our country and the discovery of new discoveries in science remain the main reasons for this. Drawing on the rules of rhythm, symmetry, and asymmetry in fine arts classes can help you master some of the geometry of drawing from the lives of great artists. Particular attention should be paid to the connection of the subject of fine arts with literature. Because there are great opportunities for the connection of these two objects. These possibilities can be seen in such topics as illustration of the content of works of art, work on the sketch of the book cover. It is also important to link art classes to

subjects such as history, geography, drawing, physics, music, physical education, and chemistry. In the thematic planning of fine arts lessons, it is better to combine it with various seasonal school activities. Nowadays, with the development of public education, in order to conduct each lesson at a high level, it is necessary to introduce the system of cabinets and conduct lessons on the basis of demonstrations. The study of the laws of color in the works of fine arts, especially those that reflect the themes of applied art, the study of the life and work of great masters is inconceivable without an office, our technical means and visual aids. This saves the teacher time. Gives a detailed understanding of the place and objects to be studied. Creates an emotional aesthetic situation in the classroom. Facilitates the understanding of works of art and leads to a thorough mastery of all learning materials.

In short, if the elements of the pattern are taught to students in a simplified way in the subjects of applied arts in the lessons of fine arts, the elements of the pattern can be taught not only to third-graders, but also to first-graders. At the same time, finger movements, memory enhancement and further development of students' worldviews by connecting the dots play an important role. The interdependence of the educational and upbringing processes in the fine arts classes focuses on ideological, political-ethical, aesthetic and labor education.

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